

most of the product got precipitated, which was filtered off. The mother liquor on concentration gave more of the product IIIa. This product was recrystallised from hot benzene to give pure IIIa, m.p. 203° (yield 72%).

IIIb and IIIc were prepared in similar manner and data for these products are given in Table 1.

Compd. No.	m.p.*	Yield	Molecular formula**
IIIa	203	72%	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ NO ₂
IIIb	245	65%	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ NO ₂ Br
IIIc	225	50%	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₄

* All the melting points are uncorrected.
** All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

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A New Degradation of Atisine to C₂₀-aminocarbamol

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VON Braun cyanogen bromide reaction has been employed by a number of workers for the degradation of alkaloids during structure elucidation^{1,2}. The reaction proceeds by an attack at the basic tertiary nitrogen atom. The reagent usually effects the C-N bond cleavage on the less hindered side to yield an alkylbromide and a disubstituted cyanamide. The latter on acid or alkali hydrolysis yields a secondary amine, thus providing a useful procedure for N-dealkylation.

Survey of literature shows no report on the reaction of cyanogen bromide with atisine. It was, therefore, considered of interest to explore this reaction in case of atisine. For the present study atisine (asatsinium chloride (I) (C₂₂H₃₄N⁺O₂Cl⁻), m.p. 311°) was subjected to reduction with sodium borohydride according to the method of Edward to yield dihydroatisine (II) C₂₂H₃₅NO₂, m.p. 161-161.5°,

M⁺m/e 345³. The latter on subsequent reaction with cyanogen bromide in dry solvent ether at room temperature for 24 hours gave an N-nitrile(III), crystallised from absolute ethanol, C₂₁H₃₀N₂O, m.p. 265° in 86% yield.

$\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ cm⁻¹ 3336 (OH); 1643, 892 (C=CH₂); 1079, 1067 (>CH-OH). No bands assignable to C≡N group could be noted in the IR spectrum. The mass spectrum of III does not show any parent peak, but a M-54 peak (m/e 272) due to C₁₅H₁₁O⁺ in 100 per cent. abundance indicating an initial loss of CH₂=N-C≡N as neutral species from the highly unstable M⁺. Further loss of C₄-Me as a radical gives C₁₁H₇O⁺ (m/e 257) which suffers Retro Diels-Alder cleavage of the bicyclo-octane system comprising rings C and D with loss of CH₂=CH₂ to yield C₁₀H₇O⁺ species (m/e 229). The latter (after rearrangement) undergoes fission along path 'a' or 'b' to yield C₉H₇O⁺ (m/e 135), C₈H₅⁺ (m/e 121), C₈H₁₁⁺ (m/e 107), C₇H₉⁺ (m/e 93) and C₆H₇⁺ (m/e 79) species as other prominent peaks. The fragmentation pattern of III is given in chart 1.

A study of the mass spectrum of dihydroatisine shows a similar fragmentation pattern. The M⁺ ion C₂₂H₃₅NO₂ (m/e 345) suffers a loss of C₂₂ carbon as CH₂OH radical to give a M-31 ion radical C₂₁H₃₃NO⁺ peak at m/e 314 in 100 per cent. abundance. The latter then undergoes the fission of hetero ring E to yield the same C₁₀H₇O⁺ species (m/e 272) as observed in the mass spectrum of III. Similar fragmentation pattern further confirm the similar position of the rings A, B, C, D and E in the known pentacyclic skeleton in both cases.

Acid hydrolysis of III with 10% boiling HCl for about 2 hours followed by extraction with ether after basification with alkali gave on evaporation the crude C₂₀-aminocarbamol(IV). The latter was purified by passing through a column of activated

alumina. The pure product melted at 154-154.5°; this did not depress the melting point on admixture with an authentic sample of C₂₀-aminocarbinal prepared by following the method of Dvornik et al⁴.

Experimental

Preparation of N-nitrile of Dihydroatisine :

To an ether solution of cyanogen bromide was added dihydroatisine (0.1 mole) in ether. The contents were kept at room temperature for 24 hours. The crystals of N-nitrile were filtered at the pump and recrystallised from ethanol to get pure N-nitrile, m.p. 265° (yield 86.4%).

Hydrolysis of N-nitrile to C₂₀-aminocarbinal :

The above N-nitrile (0.1 mole) was refluxed with dilute HCl (20 ml) for about 2 hours. The contents were cooled and basified with ammonia and

extracted with ether. Removal of ether gave C₂₀-aminocarbinal which was recrystallised from ethanol to yield pure C₂₀-aminocarbinal, m.p. 154° (yield 92%), m.m.p. with authentic sample 154°.

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Amoebicidal and Fungicidal Activity in New Imidazoles*

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THE discovery and success of metronidazole (2-methyl-5-nitro-1-ethanol imidazole) as a potent amoebicidal agent, stimulated research in imidazole chemistry. A number of compounds having various substituents at 1, 2 and 5 position of imidazole ring have been synthesised and tested for various therapeutic effects¹⁻³. The broad antifungal spectrum of micronazole (imidazolylmethyl derivative of 2,4-dichlorobenzyl ether) is well known. The biological activity of micronazole and other imidazole derivatives as antifungal agent has in recent years, aroused interest in the synthesis of new derivatives. It has been further found that 1-aryl substitution in imidazole nucleus^{4,5} enhances the microbial activity. In addition to this the divalent sulphur-containing molecules such as 'NCS' have also been found to possess good antimicrobial properties^{6,7}.

From the above lead we have synthesised some new 1-aryl 2-mercapto substituted benzoyl imidazoles and tested for their amoebicidal and fungicidal activity.

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